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D4.2 Online educational material (final version)

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
FTT	Fast Track Training
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
TA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The final version of the Online educational material deliverable for WP4 "Capacity Building and Training" encapsulates the core educational training provided to the VITALISE community and external researchers and practitioners. This document serves as a centralized repository, offering insights into the educational activities crafted throughout the VITALISE project.

The primary aim of this deliverable is to present a comprehensive overview of the educational endeavors undertaken within the project under WP4. It stands as a cornerstone of knowledge, providing guidance for future educational programmes focused on integrating Living Labs as Research Infrastructures, applying the Living Lab Approach, understanding the path to market for new products and services, and offering directives to researchers joining the VITALISE Transnational Access Programme.

The document is structured into eight main chapters:

- **Chapter 1 “Introduction”** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, its related aspects, and the purpose of this document.
- **Chapter 2 “Overview Capacity Building and Training Activities”** presents a mapping of the Capacity Building and Training Activities developed in WP4.
- **Chapter 3 “Online Educational Materials”** includes a general overview of the online educational materials designed and implemented in WP4.
- **Chapter 4 “One-Page Presentation Educational Materials”** offers a concise overview of both online educational materials in a one-page format, enhancing accessibility for readers to delve into and explore the content.
- **Chapter 5 “Repository Online Materials”** presents the repository for the online materials.
- **Chapter 6 “Conclusions”** provides concluding remarks for this deliverable.
- **Chapter 7 “Works Cited”** includes works cited in the deliverable.
- **Chapter 8 “Appendices”** contains the annexes of this deliverable.

Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens Living Lab Infrastructures to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing, and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP4

Work Package 4 (WP4), titled "Capacity Building and Training," is an important WP of the VITALISE project, emphasizing the development of knowledge materials to aid researchers, practitioners and enthusiasts in understanding and applying the principles of Living Labs.

Key tasks within this work package include organizing summer schools, webinars, university courses and training programs. These initiatives aim to equip future researchers and practitioners with the necessary understanding of the value and potential of Living Labs as research infrastructures. Additionally, WP4 is responsible for producing essential materials for training and educational purposes.

1.3 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to showcase the completed version of the educational materials developed in WP4, available in online format. It compiles these materials into a concise, one-page format for easy reading and potential use as a reference in upcoming capacity building endeavours.

D4.2 Online educational material (final version) showcase the educational material developed during the latter stage of the project. This content is a product of Task 4.2 "Online educational material and training programmes", and it includes the efforts undertaken within Task 4.1 "Organization of summer schools for young Researchers", Task 4.4 "Fast track training", Task 4.5 "Design and implementation of common postgraduate courses" and Task 4.6 "Boosting commercialization potential of research results".

2 OVERVIEW CAPACITY BUILDING AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES

WP4 developed four training programs throughout the project lifecycle, starting from month 6 (September 2021) until month 36 (March 2024). The training programs were designed as summer schools, bootcamps, master course webinars, and fast track trainings. Each program created a set of educational materials. This section will provide an overview of the objectives and methodology of each training program, while Section 3 will showcase the educational materials produced by these programs.

The training activities are outlined in a structured manner. These activities are presented as follows:

- **Summer Schools**
 - Summer School 2022
 - Summer School 2023
- **Commercialization Bootcamps**
 - Bootcamp 2022
 - Bootcamp 2023
 - Pitch Clinic
- **Fast Track trainings**
 - Fast Track training 2022
 - Fast Track training 2023
- **Master Course Webinars**

2.1 Summer Schools

The VITALISE project hosted two summer schools in 2022 and 2023. These events were designed to offer comprehensive training to researchers globally, covering the implementation of the Living Lab approach in their studies and the integration of Living Lab Research Infrastructures and their services into health and wellbeing research projects.

Participants had the opportunity to explore Open Innovation and Living Lab tools, methods, and services, enhancing their research capabilities and enabling them to pursue innovative scientific endeavours.

2.1.1 Summer School 2022

Main goal: to provide capacity for researchers to access research infrastructures and Living Labs

When: 6 and 7 July in Marathon, Greece

Target audience: researchers interested in accessing research infrastructures and Living Labs

Organized by: ENOLL with the support from all the VITALISE partners (and especially AUTH, LAUREA, LICALAB, TREBAG, GAIA, SIT, UPM, AV, LLSA)

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-summer-school-2022/>

The VITALISE Summer School 2022 was jointly organised and co-located with the [School As Living Labs \(SALL\) / FOODSHIFT Summer School 2022](#).

Day 1 Living Labs methods & tools for researchers		Trainer/s
09:00 am– 10:00 am	Welcome and objective Living Labs basics, benefits, and challenges	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL) Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)
10:00 am– 11:00 am	How researchers can be involved and use Living Labs in their daily job: case studies	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)
11:00 am– 12:00 pm	Tour de table: get to know each other	Leidy Enriquez (ENoLL)
12:00 pm– 1:00 pm	Living Labs services for researchers applied to case studies	Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)
1:00 pm– 2:00 pm	<i>Lunch Break</i>	
2:00 pm– 4:00 pm	Hands on exercise on selected methods & services for small research design and peer to peer learning	Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)

Day 2 Co-creating with Living Labs to improve your research		Trainer/s
10:00 am– 11:00 am	IPRs and owners of the data within Living Labs	Alexandra Anagnostopoulou (AUTH)
11:00 am– 12:00 pm	Experimentation & co-creation in a real-life environment	Beatriz Merino (UPM)
12:00pm– 1:00 pm	Hands on exercise: co-creation session on your selected research cases	Session moderated by Beatriz Merino (UPM)
1:00 pm– 2:00 pm	Lunch Break	
2:00 pm– 3:00 pm	How to improve your research through Living Labs	Eva Kehayia (McGill)
3:00 pm– 4:00 pm	Inspirational session with representatives from research projects where living labs were included	Antonid Billis, LifeChamps project Despoina Mantziari, URBANOME project Annita Varela, InAdvance project
4:00 pm– 5:00 pm	Joint SALL & VITALISE Summer School Workshop	Workshop facilitators: Leidy Enriquez (ENoLL) Despoina Petsani (AUTH)

Table 1 First VITALISE Summer School Agenda

2022 Course Objectives:

1. Engage participants in networking and peer-to-peer learning opportunities with experienced trainers from the Living Lab community.
2. Guide participants in creating a comprehensive roadmap for conducting research using the Living Lab methodology, with support and guidance from VITALISE trainers.

2.1.2 Summer School 2023

Main goal: to provide researchers, practitioners, students effective training both on how to implement the Living Lab methodology in their studies, as well as involve living labs Research Infrastructures and their services in their Health and Wellbeing research studies.

When: 8 and 9 June 2023 Bilbao, Spain

Target audience: Researchers, students, teachers and living lab beginners interested in applying the Living Lab methodology and tools in their academic and business contexts.

Organized by: ENoLL with the support from all the VITALISE partners (and especially AUTH, LAUREA, LICALAB, TREBAG, GAIA, SIT, UPM, AV, LLSA)

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-summer-school-2023/>

Day 1 (Thursday 08 June 2023) Developing your own research through Living Labs		Trainer/s
09:15 am– 09:30 am	Registrations & Welcome	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)
09:30 am– 10:00 am	Icebreaker and get to know each other	Leidy Enriquez (ENoLL)
10:00 am– 10:30 am	Living Labs 101: benefits, pitfalls, and challenges	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)
10:30 am– 11:00 am	Living Labs innovation process and services	Teemu Santonen (LAUREA)
11:00 am– 11:30 pm	Creating research through Living Labs	Eva Kehayia (McGill)
11:30 pm– 01:00 pm	Hands on session: Emerging research design and innovation processes through LL	Teemu Santonen (LAUREA) + Eva Kehayia (McGill)
1:00 pm– 2:00 pm	Lunch Break	
2:00 pm– 3:00 pm	Living Labs Governance & Business models	Jokin Garatea (GAIA)
3:00 pm– 4:00 pm	Experimentation, stakeholder engagement & co-creation in Living Labs through case studies	Beatriz Merino (UPM)

Day 2 (Friday 09 June 2023) Putting the life into your Living Lab: VITALISE Tools		Trainers
09:30 am – 10:00 am	Welcome and introduction of the second day	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)
10:00 am – 11:00 am	Harmonization of the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab process and ICT tools	Despoina Petsani (AUTH)
11:00 am – 12:00 pm	Hands-on workshop on VITALISE system for data discovery and analysis	Gorka Epelde (VICOM)
12:00 pm – 1:00 pm	Workshop on the VITALISE Living Lab Lexicon	Eva Kehayia (McGill)
1:00 pm – 1:30 pm	Wrap up, opportunities for collaboration and conclusions	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)

Table 2 Second VITALISE Summer School Agenda

2023 Course Objectives:

1. Support European researchers, students, teachers, and practitioners in understanding Living Lab methodologies within Health and ICT sectors to boost career growth.
2. Expand access for external researchers to global Living Lab research infrastructures to enhance academic collaboration.
3. Foster cross-European collaboration in co-creating services through open innovation and Living Lab methodologies, focusing on health & wellbeing while including industrial and technological innovation.

The first edition of the VITALISE Summer School, held in Athens, Greece in July 2022, focused on aiding external researchers in implementing Living Lab methodologies.

The second edition, held in Bilbao, Spain in June 2023, focused on support researchers, students, teachers, and practitioners in developing their own Living Lab projects. Through case studies and hands-on workshops, participants overcame common challenges in Living Lab research. The second iteration of the Summer School also adopted a broader and more expansive approach, intentionally designed to accommodate a spectrum of fields and expertise beyond the realm of health.

2.2 Commercialization Bootcamps

VITALISE Commercialization Bootcamps, the Bootcamp days focused on a practical approach for researchers and practitioners who were interested in understanding the path to market for new products and services.

Innovative research can lead to innovative products and services provided there is a team with the capacity and desire to take these solutions all the way into the market. Too often, researchers are dedicated more fully to the academic results of their work, and less so to their exploitation. The Bootcamps focused on providing increased understanding of the pathways to commercialization that researchers can follow, as well as better insights into the various levels that reviewers use to rate product, business, and investment readiness.

Two Bootcamps were organized over the course of the VITALISE project.

2.2.1 Bootcamp 2022

Main goal: to increase participants' understanding on how to exploit research results by including key elements of business building and planning appropriate paths to market.

When: 20 September, Turin, Italy

Target audience: researchers interested in accessing research infrastructures and Living Labs

Organized by: ENoLL with the support of all WP4 partners (and especially AV)

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-commercialisation-bootcamp-2022/>

The first session took place during the OpenLivingLab Days in September 2022, in Turin Italy. This was a three-hour session targeted at researchers and LL professionals. The bootcamp began with familiarizing participants with the Innovation Radar and KTH Innovation readiness model and provided an overview of the modified tool which the VITALISE project developed. This tool combines elements of the KTH and the Innovation Radar along with additional functionality to examine research results from a more holistic perspective. It was followed by a hands-on exercise, where participants watched a demonstration of the tool to evaluate a start-up case in real-time. Participants were guided through the evaluation process to learn how to assess the maturity and current development status of projects, including those supported by Living Labs, and were able to ask questions of the founders regarding their challenges in moving from research to prototype and marketable product.

VITALISE Bootcamp 2022		Contributors
16:00 pm – 16:10 pm	Welcome and objectives	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL) Martina Desole (ENoLL)
16:10 pm – 17:00 pm	Understand the tactics to commercialize your project	Paraskevi Giourka (AV)
17:00 pm – 17:50 pm	Assess the commercialization potential of your project	Adriane Trash (AV)
17:50 pm – 18:00 pm	Conclusions and next opportunities from VITALISE Capacity Building Programme	Francesca Spagnoli (ENoLL)

Table 3 First VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp Agenda

2.2.2 Bootcamp 2023

Main goal: to increase participants' understanding on how to exploit research results by including key elements of business building and planning appropriate paths to market.

When: 06 and 07 June Bilbao, Spain

Target audience: Researchers interested in accessing research infrastructures and Living Labs

Organized by: ENoLL with the support of all WP4 partners (and especially AV)

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-commercialisation-bootcamp-2022/>

The second session took place over two days, just before the VITALISE Summer School held in Bilbao, Spain, in June 2023. It was targeted at researchers and Living Lab professionals. The content was designed to be interactive, featuring a blend of presentations and group work covering topics such as Design Thinking & User Analysis, Commercialization Pathways, Intellectual Property, and Investment Basics (a full list of content can be found below). Participants actively engaged with each other and the workshop hosts, collaborating to create mock user profiles, pricing strategies, and value propositions for a Case Study-based hypothetical startup.

The presentations were supplemented by two sessions with guest speakers – founders of healthtech startups. Each speaker discussed their company's journey from research to commercialization. The first company focuses on a robotic personal care assistant aimed at elderly or homebound individuals and their caregivers. As their product is at the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) stage, it provided an excellent opportunity to explore various core business questions, including marketing, sales and distribution strategy, pricing policy and structure, and fundraising.

The second speaker, Mr. Eduard Guerrero of Loop Diagnostics, offered valuable insights into the challenges encountered at each stage of the commercialization journey. He provided a detailed presentation covering technical, legal, and financial aspects required to transition a diagnostic device from theoretical beginnings in the laboratory to a functional prototype ready for full commercial production.

Day 1 (Tuesday 06 June 2023)		Trainer/s
09:30 am – 10:00 am	Welcome and Ice Breaker	Adriane Thrash (AV)
10:00 am – 10:15 am	Intro to the commercialization process and the VITALISE Bootcamp	Adriane Thrash (AV)
10:15 am – 10:30 am	Commercialization Case Study – AccelUp	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)
10:30 am – 11:30 am	Business Models, and Selecting Appropriate Pathways for Commercialization (with related resources)	Anthology Ventures
11:30 am – 11:45 am	Coffee Break	
11:45am – 12:00 pm	Lecture; Participants divide into teams.	
12:00 pm – 1:00 pm	Group Work #1 User Profiling and customer needs	Group Work #2 Problem - Solution Fit (Value

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	(Use Accelup as active case study; participants will interview the LLS, after guidance on what and how they need to ask)	Proposition Canvas	
1:00 pm – 2:00 pm	Lunch Break		
2:00 pm – 2:45 pm	Group Work #3 work on revenue Streams		
2:45 pm – 3:00 pm	Intro Market research and competition analysis		Adriane Thrash (AV)
3:00 pm – 3:30 pm	Group Work #3 work on Market research and competition analysis (Desk Research, Competition Matrix)		
3:30 pm – 4:00pm	Team presentations & reflections (End of day)		Adriane Thrash (AV)

Day 2 (Wednesday 07 June 2023)		Trainer/s
09:30 am – 10:00 am	Assessment tools for commercialization potential + Example (the KTH Tool)	Adriane Thrash (AV)
10:00 am – 10:30 am	Commercialization Elements (Business Model, Legal Form, Key partners, Team, ...)	Adriane Thrash (AV)
10:30 am – 11:30 am	Group Evaluation: with Evdokimos (run the KTH tool – each team will be given 1-2 of the evaluation scales to discuss)	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL)
11:30 am – 11:45 am	Coffee Break	
11:45 am – 12:20 pm	Investment Basics for Tech Startups: Funding Cycles & Structures	Adriane Thrash (AV)
12:20 pm – 13:20 pm	Loop Diagnostics: Start-up Commercialization Case Study (Guest Speaker) Discussion & Q/A	Adriane Thrash (AV)
13:20 pm	Depart to excursion.	Adriane Thrash (AV)

Table 4 Second VITALISE Commercialisation Bootcamp Agenda

2.2.3 Pitch Clinic

In addition to the Bootcamps, VITALISE organized in February 2024 an online Pitch Clinic aimed at researchers. The content was delivered over three days of online webinars, featuring detailed presentations from several speakers on topics such as Communicating Research Results to Lay Audiences, Understanding Investors, and Commercialization.

Guest speakers included Stergios Anastasiadis of Genesis Venture Capital, who discussed the challenges of investing in research and tech-transfer startups, and Antti Heikila of Acceler8 Venture Builder, who covered sources of support from the European Union available for research-based startups (EIT, EIC).

The final day included an in-depth examination of a prototype-stage healthtech startup's pitch deck, followed by a detailed analysis and Q&A session with the founders. The clinic was promoted through LinkedIn events and other social media channels.

Main goal: Communicating Research Results to Lay Audiences, Understanding Investors, and Commercialization.

When: 13, 15, 22 February 2024, online

Target audience: researchers interested in accessing research infrastructures and Living Labs

Organized by: AV

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/pitch-clinic-event-save-the-dates/>

Day 1, 13 Feb 2024		
15:00 pm – 16:00 pm	Understanding how Investors Think and What They are Looking For	Adriane Thrash (AV)
16:00 pm – 17:00 pm	Mastering the Art of Persuasive Presentations for Research-based Start-ups	Adriane Thrash (AV)
17:00 pm – 17:30 pm	Why We Say Yes to Tech Transfer Start-ups	Stergios Anastasiadis, Genesis Ventures

Day 2, 15 Feb 2024		
15:00 pm – 16:00 pm	Creating a Clear Value Proposition	Adriane Thrash (AV)
16:00 pm – 17:00 pm	TRL to BRL – the Path to Commercialization with EIC Support	Antti Heikkilä, Aceller8 Venture Builder
17:00 pm – 17:30 pm	From Funded Project to Funded Company	Start-up Founder

Day 3, 22 Feb 2024		
15:00 pm – 17:30 pm	Pitching Your Business Concept	Adriane Thrash (AV)

Table 5 First VITALISE Pitch Clinic Agenda

2.3 Fast Track trainings

Fast Track Trainings were specifically crafted for all researchers accepted into the VITALISE Transnational Access Programme (TA). These sessions served as an introduction to the TA programme, aiding participants in understanding the activities involved and ensuring the research conducted within the framework of the VITALISE Transnational Access Programme maintained high standards of quality. The Fast Track Training program comprised two activities: one conducted prior to Transnational Access, and another held on-site.

Main goal: Provide concise directives to researchers admitted into the VITALISE Transnational Access Programme (TA) regarding the tasks to be undertaken.

When: Based on TA timings 2022 and 2023

Target audience: researchers admitted into the TA

Organized by: AV

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/fast-track-trainings/>

Day 1 (training block 1-4)		Day 2 (training block 5-8)
09:30 am – 10:30 am	Coffee and welcome, Icebreaker	Methodology: Design thinking, co-creation, focus group, human factor study, ...
10:30am – 11:00 am	Break	Break
11:00 am – 12:30 pm	Meet the colleagues	Methodology workshop: (3 options)
12:30 pm – 13:30 pm	Lunch	Lunch
13:30 pm – 5:00 pm	Short intro into LL LL services Ethical framework	Panel management – Target groups and how to engage them
14:00 pm – 15:30 pm	Break	Break
15:30 pm – 16:30 pm	VITALISE: The importance of harmonisation	Free block E.g. LiCalab: How to deal with companies – business model preparation

Table 6 VITALISE Fast Track Trainings Agenda

First two blocks: Introductions from visiting researchers and hosting Living Labs, followed by an icebreaker to foster creativity and openness.

Third block: Understanding Living Labs, roles, services offered, and ethical considerations.

Fourth block: Emphasizing harmonization in VITALISE, exploring project objectives and joint research activities.

Second day: Methodologies training, including design thinking and practical workshops.

Sixth block: Methodology workshop options: study elaboration, method/tool demonstration, or UX design speed testing template.

Seventh block: Panel management and engaging target groups, discussing panel databases and recruitment strategies.

Final block: Customized training based on hosting Living Lab expertise, such as business model preparation.

Self-reflection diary: Utilize NoteTheBook platform for interactive learning experiences, accessible at <https://vitalise.trebag.hu/>, resulting in personalized PDF booklets for researchers by the end of the TA.

2.4 Master Course Webinars

Main goal: Equip with the knowledge, tools, and strategies to thrive in the dynamic world of innovation management and collaborative research.

When: 11 Oct till 13 Dec 2023

Target audience: Researchers, Living Lab practitioners, students

Organized by: ENoLL with the support from all the VITALISE partners (and especially AUTH, LAUREA, LICALAB, TREBAG, GAIA, SIT, UPM, AV, LLSA)

Webpage: <https://vitalise-project.eu/innovate-to-thrive-mastering-living-labs-and-collaborative-innovation/>

The Master Course Webinars consisted of an 8-part series aimed at providing participants with essential knowledge, tools, and strategies to excel in the dynamic realm of innovation, Living Labs application and collaborative research. These webinars covered various topics, including:

1. Building bridges: transdisciplinary communication and networking strategies
2. Exploring theoretical foundations of innovation typology and innovation ecosystems: unleashing the power of collaborative innovation
3. Living labs
4. To panel or not to panel
5. What's the real problem?
- 6 The "how" the "what" the "when" and "with whom" of measurement in living lab research
7. Empowering collaborative innovation: co-creation and user testing methods unveiled
8. Driving innovation success: unleashing the power of user-centric research design for your next project

3 ONLINE EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS

3.1 What, How, When and Where

Figure 1 Timeline WP4 Tasks

Training Program	Access link 	Educational material produced
Summer School 2022	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-summer-school-2022-training-materials/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living Lab Basic, benefits and Challenges • Living Lab Innovation Process and tools • Protocol Template • Protocol Examples • Protocol for ethics • How researchers can be involved and use Living labs in their daily job. Case studies • Experimentation and Co-creation in real environments • Data Management Ownership LLs
Summer School 2023	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/presentations https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimentation, stakeholder engagement & co-creation in Living Labs through case studies • Governance matrix • Hands on session: Emerging research design and innovation processes through LL • Harmonization of the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab process and ICT tools • Hands-on workshop on VITALISE system for data discovery and analysis • Workshop on the VITALISE Living Lab Lexicon.
Commercialization Bootcamp 2022	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-commercialisation-bootcamp-2022/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercialisation deck • Commercialisation Pathway • KTH IRL Dashboard • Customer User Analysis • VITALISE Fundraising strategy guide

D4.2 Online educational material (final version)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VITALISE Investment basics • VITALISE market sizing • VITALISE launching the MVP
Commercialization Bootcamp 2023	https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/presentations https://www.slideshare.net/VITALISEProject/documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercialization, Design thinking & user analysis • Investment Basics for startups • Business Models • Revenue Structures • Leveraging IP research
Pitch Clinic	<p><u>Day 1 video:</u> Passcode: \$H?KFD2g</p> <p><u>Day 2 video:</u> Passcode: hkIKb4H&</p> <p><u>Day 3 video:</u> Passcode: mnqm9Dd*</p> <p><u>https://vitalise-project.eu/pitch-clinic-event-save-the-dates/</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding how Investors Think and What They are Looking for Seminar with Anthology Ventures • Mastering the Art of Persuasive Presentations for Research-based Startups Workshop with Anthology Ventures • Why We Say Yes to Tech Transfer Startups”Interview with Stergios Anastasiadis, Genesis Ventures • Creating a Clear Value Proposition Workshop with Anthology Ventures • TRL to BRL – the Path to Commercialization with EIC Support Presentation by Antti Heikkilä, Aceller8 Venture Builder • From Funded Project to Funded Company Interview with a Startup Founder • Pitching Your Business Concept Group workshop with Anthology Ventures
Fast track trainings 2022 & 2023	<p><u>https://vitalise-project.eu/fast-track-training-2022/</u></p> <p><u>https://vitalise.trebag.hu/</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short intro to Living Labs Services-Ethical framework TA researchers • VITALISE The importance of Harmonization • Methodologies TA researchers • VITALISE Methodologies Workshop • Target Groups- panel management TA-researchers • How to deal with companies- business model preparation – TA Researchers • Self-reflection diary: NoteTheBook platform for interactive learning experiences, accessible at https://vitalise.trebag.hu/

<p>Master Course Webinars</p>	<p>https://vitalise-project.eu/innovate-to-thrive-mastering-living-labs-and-collaborative-innovation/</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Webinars and additional materials shared with participants only <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Building bridges: transdisciplinary communication and networking strategies ○ Exploring theoretical foundations of innovation typology and innovation ecosystems: unleashing the power of collaborative innovation ○ Living labs ○ To panel or not to panel ○ What’s the real problem? ○ 6 The “how” the “what” the “when” and “with whom” of measurement in living lab research ○ Empowering collaborative innovation: co-creation and user testing methods unveiled ○ Driving innovation success: unleashing the power of user-centric research design for your next project ● Extra templates for Research Plan ● Additional one to one support for Research plan
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Table 7 Training Programs and Educational Material Produced

Table 8 Overview Training Programs, Participants Trained

Training	Designed for 	Format 	Date launched 	Total trained people
Summer Schools	First edition: Researchers Second edition: Researchers, students, teachers and living lab beginners	In person	First edition: 6, 7 July 2022 Second edition: 8, 9 June 2023	76 2022: 37 2023: 39
Commercialization Bootcamps	First edition: Researchers Second edition: Researchers, startups	In person Online	First edition: 20 September 2022 Second edition: 08 June 2023	45 2022: 24 2023: 21
Pitch Clinic	Researchers, startups	Online	13, 15, 22 February 2024	11
Fast track trainings	Researchers admitted to the TAs.	In person & Online	Along 2022- 2023	48
Master Course Webinars	Researchers, post-graduate students, teachers and living lab beginners	Online	11 October until 13 December 2023	93

3.2 Total number of people trained

The internal reports for each program contain more detailed data regarding gender, field of study/work, country, among other variables. This report, however, specifically concentrates on the quantity of individuals accessing the Capacity Building and training programs from WP4 exclusively. Trainings and activities from other packages are addressed in their respective reports or deliverables.

Figure 2 Overview Trained People

4 ONE-PAGER PRESENTATION EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS

This section showcases some educational materials produced in WP4 under the four different programs.

Figure 3 Cover Presentation Training Programmes

4.1 Summer Schools

Summer School materials

01

- PowerPoints
- Recordings
- Printable protocols templates
- Exercises
- Certificates of assistance

Figure 4 Vitalise Summer School ppt 2022

Figure 5 Vitalise Summer School ppt 2023

Key outcomes

Empowering Global Researchers: Vitalise Summer Schools empower a diverse range of participants worldwide with a robust curriculum on Living Lab methodology, fostering active learning and collaboration.

International Engagement: With over 16 countries represented (VITALISE, 2023) the Summer Schools facilitate a rich exchange of ideas, promoting cross-cultural understanding and inclusivity among students and professionals.

Building Research Networks: The success of the Summer Schools fosters connections among researchers across continents, encouraging ongoing collaboration and support.

Driving Innovation and Research: Participants leverage Living Lab methodology to unlock insights, revolutionize product development, and advance research outcomes in various fields.

Broader Impact: Beyond academia, industry, government, and non-profit sectors recognize the value of Living Lab training, fostering collaborations to address real-world challenges and user needs effectively.

4.2 Commercialization Bootcamps

Commercialization Bootcamps

02

- PowerPoints
- Exercises
- One to one guidance
- Access to Note the Book

Figure 6 Brochure Bootcamp 2022

Key outcomes

One of the notable accomplishments in the second edition of the VITALISE Summer School and Bootcamp was the diversification of backgrounds among the participants. This achievement underscores the outstanding harmonization across various fields and underscores the adaptability and utility of the Living Lab approach across diverse spheres, all in pursuit of a collaborative methodology.

The Bootcamps integrated theoretical seminars with hands-on workshops, focusing on:

Introduction to Entrepreneurship Principles: Participants gained insights into developing ideas into viable business concepts, covering essential elements such as identifying needs/problems, validating with customers, understanding the competitive landscape, basic finance, and effective pitching techniques.

Acceleration Bootcamp: Built upon foundational training, practical exercises based on industry-standard Start-up Theory and Practices were employed to aid participants in refining their business strategies and tactics. Topics included business modeling, go-to-market strategy, scaling, revenue models, partnership development, and fundraising strategies.

Figure 7 Workshop Pitch clinic 2024

4.3 Fast Track trainings

Fast track trainings

03

- PowerPoints
- Recordings
- Exercises
- Pitch Clinic Workshops

Key outcomes

The FFT program had 5 training blocks such as Harmonization, Methodology Theory, Methodology workshop and Panel Management.

Participants engaged in a comprehensive 2-day fast track training (FTT) program designed to familiarize them with Living Labs. The program encompassed diverse topics, including Living Lab introduction and services, the significance of harmonization, Living Lab methodology, panel management, and strategies for engaging target groups.

More detailed information can be found under the Fast Track Trainings reports.

Figure 8 NotetheBook, platform used by FFT participants.

4.4 Master Course Webinars

Master Course Webinars

04

- PowerPoints
- Recordings
- Webinars
- Extra tutoring Research Plan
- Research Plan printable template
- Certificates of competition
- Skills Survey for Master Course Webinar

EXPLORING THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATION TYPOLOGY AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS: UNLEASHING THE POWER OF COLLABORATIVE INNOVATION

16th October 2023 at 15.00 CET

the knowledge to develop innovative and sustainable business models, and drive long-term value for your organization and society while addressing pressing global challenges.

Gain a comprehensive understanding of the key characteristics inherent to various types of innovation, as well as their profound impact on the innovation management process. Acquire a deep understanding of the key concepts and methodologies in various human and user-centric development approaches, empowering you to create impactful user experiences in an agile and iterative manner across diverse domains. Strengthen your skills in orchestrating and governing open innovation ecosystems and public-private-people partnerships, enabling you to foster innovation from diverse ecosystems, while mastering partnership dynamics, trust building, and knowledge transfer across all network actors. Explore the convergence of sustainability and innovation, acquire

BUILDING BRIDGES: TRANSDISCIPLINARY COMMUNICATION AND NETWORKING STRATEGIES

11th October 2023 at 15.00 CET

Webinar aims to provide participants a comprehensive understanding of the importance and practical application of innovation in the context of Living Labs (LLs). It will use real-life examples and data to demonstrate the scope and benefits of incorporating innovation into LLs. It consists of four parts: outlining objectives and learning outcomes, differentiating course participants and promoting engagement, implementing the 5E teaching method for postgraduate curricula, and emphasizing transdisciplinary communication and collaboration. In addition, the module addresses platform functionality, interaction and networking in the online postgraduate programme. It explores the pedagogical value of digital media integration and strategies for effective networking using tools

such as social bookmarking, social networking, web quests and video tools.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) Scope and benefits of Innovation in LLS, 2) Real-life examples 3) Effective networking tools.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) definition and Sources of Innovation, 2) innovation typology and examples, 3) explain how to make transition from closed to collaborative innovation and operating within innovation ecosystems, 4) describe collaborative innovation terminology and degrees of user involvement, 5) give examples of variations in research, development, and innovation processes, 6) explain the process from User-Centred Design to implementation science, 7) describes different innovation maturity levels.

LIVING LABS' FUNDAMENTALS

25th October 2023 at 15.00 CET

Experience an enlightening webinar, "Living Labs' Fundamentals," where we dive into the essentials of the Living Labs approach. Explore how the Living Labs can act as research infrastructures to support and boost innovation projects across various domains. Additionally, uncover their pivotal role in expediting innovations to market, serving as a powerful catalyst for progress. Unlock the potential of Living Lab business models, business plans, and sustainability strategies that underpin their long-term success. We'll provide valuable insights into these crucial aspects. To conclude, we'll unveil the Living Lab labeling framework and evaluation process, conducted by the European Network of Living Labs. This webinar is your gateway to understanding and harnessing the power of

Living Labs for innovation excellence. Join us on this educational journey as we unravel the essence of Living Labs' fundamentals and their impact on innovation.

TO PANEL OR NOT TO PANEL

31th October 2023 at 15.00 CET

This webinar looks at panel management in all its aspects. What are the benefits but also the limitations of a user panel. How and where to start? Once in place, it has to be managed and maintained. During this lesson you learn from LiCalab's experience in recruiting and managing the user community. Furthermore, a well-managed user panel is a source of data that can be used in a smart way, member profiles can be further segmented and enriched. You will learn about possible software tools to collect these data.

WHAT'S THE REAL PROBLEM

8th November 2023 at 15.00 CET

Before even start to design, it is paramount to really understand the user's need. Much is there to learn about empathizing with your end user and uncover the real problem and challenge. There is a difference between identifying the need (needs assessment) and the need analysis. In this webinar you take a deeper dive into the problem framing: the who, why what, where and when. Webinar will provide you with tools to plan a needs assessment for individuals or communities.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) living labs' essentials, 2) describe living labs as research infrastructure, 3) explain how living lab services can accelerate access to market, 4) describes living lab business model, business plan and sustainability, 5) innovation projects and activities carried out within living labs, 6) explain European Network of Living Labs evaluation and labelling framework.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) stakeholder analysis, engagement, and profiling, 2) explain how establish and manage user panel, 3) how use Panelab community management tool.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) how to explore the real problem, 2) how to user SROI (Social Return on Investment) as tool for stakeholder engagement, 3) how to conduct needs analysis and problem definition, 4) how to do prefield testing by following human factor study principles.

THE “HOW” THE “WHAT” THE “WHEN” AND “WITH WHOM” OF MEASUREMENT IN LIVING LAB RESEARCH

22nd November 2023 at 15.00 CET

From qualitative, to quantitative and mixed methods, you will be exposed to the main research methodologies, as they relate to living lab research on various topics such as health and wellbeing. You will be introduced to various techniques of data collection as you venture in designing a project using qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methodology. From formulating a research question to identifying the appropriate strategies to answer your research question, you will design your very own measurement instruments, e.g., a short questionnaire, or prepare for a focus group. In doing so, you will also learn how to interpret the scores and findings of the different measurement instruments and techniques. Finally, you will be invited to reflect on existing measures and the

information they provide within the context of living lab research.

EMPOWERING COLLABORATIVE INNOVATION: CO-CREATION AND USER TESTING METHODS UNVEILED

5th December 2023 at 15.00 CET

Join us for an engaging webinar where we delve into the world of co-creation and testing methods, exploring the essential skills needed to drive innovation. This webinar will empower you to understand and utilize co-creation techniques for ideation, concept creation, and prototyping. Learn the best practices for facilitating co-creative workshops and techniques to engage stakeholders and end-users effectively. Explore a range of tools and virtual spaces for online workshops, ideation, and creativity boosting. Furthermore, dive into the diverse testing methods, including idea testing, concept testing, feasibility testing, prototype testing, usability testing, and real-life testing.

DRIVING INNOVATION SUCCESS: UNLEASHING THE POWER OF USER-CENTRIC RESEARCH DESIGN FOR YOUR NEXT PROJECT

13th December 2023 at 15.00 CET

Are you ready to take your projects to new heights? Unlock the Secrets to User-Centric Projects and discover the secrets to creating impactful user-centric projects while upholding ethical standards and leveraging cutting-edge concepts. Dive deep into the realm of basic ethics concepts, intellectual property rights (IPR), FAIR data, and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) – all essential elements in today's innovation landscape. Webinar will empower you with proven strategies and techniques to ensure your projects resonate with your audience. Learn how to navigate ethical challenges, protect intellectual property, harness FAIR data principle, promote Responsible Research and Innovation, and unleash the power of design thinking to create innovative solutions that truly

meet user needs. In webinar you will gain invaluable insights and techniques that will set you apart in the world of user-centric projects.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) how to formulate a Research Question, 2) searching the literature and acquiring background information via different methods, 3) how to do living lab research planning and selecting research methods for your project, 4) practical insight for Qualitative Research

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) co-creation and testing methods, 2) Techniques to facilitate co-creation workshops 3) Testing methods.

Key outcomes

Materials share knowledge on 1) Basic Ethics Concepts, 2) IPR and copyright in open innovation, 3) FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), 4) how to make research design for your own "user centric living lab project".

Living Lab Research Protocol Template

Excel-template, Word-template, Case example

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1			TRL 6	TRL 7	TRL 8	
2	What (procedures and methods)	Describe the procedures, activities, methods, templates and/or processes used in the intervention / user engagement, including any enabling or support activities.		(1) For 40 persons Physical activity level measurement and diary for 24 hours with armband sensor devices before taking part to measurement day, (2) signing the consent form and the quality of life questionnaire, (3) executing track having 11 measurement points, (4) filling extended User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ).		
3	What (materials, technologies and devices)	Describe any physical or informational materials, technologies and devices used in the intervention(s), including those provided to participants or used in intervention delivery or in training of intervention providers.		(1) Armband sensor devices and diary template for 40 participants For all participants: (1) Consent form, (2) Quality of life questionnaire, (3) score sheets x 2 for the physical fitness measurements, (4) Tools for measurement points see list* (5) General reference values and the interpretation guidelines for participants, webpage and paper (6) A security plan and training for event staff		
4	Where (Research environment)	Describe the type(s) of location(s) where the research activities and intervention is planned to occur, including any necessary infrastructure or relevant features in the location (e.g. simulation hospital, nursing home, public park)		(1) a big sports hall (2) In 24-hour measurements locations vary.		
5	How	Describe the modes of delivery (such as face to face or by some other mechanism, such as internet or telephone) of the intervention and whether it is provided individually or in a group.		(1) Armband devices participants will be invited to a specific location receive and returns the device and diary (2) In sport hall, an open access time period by following the walk-in principle. (3) In the reception participants receive instructions and questionnaires. (4) Participants are invited individually from the sport to receive		

Figure 9 Excel Living Lab Research Template

RESEARCH PROTOCOL SYNOPSIS
based on
Hoffmann, T.C., Glasziou, P.P., Boutron, I., Milne, R., Perera, R., Moher, D., Altman, D.G., Barbour, V., Macdonald, H., Johnston, M. and Lamb, S.E., 2014. Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide. Bmj, 348.

Study title	Brief name describing the project
WHY	
Study rationale / background and significance	Explain and justify shortly why this study is conducted including study background. What are the most significant theoretical and methodological premises of the project?
Study objectives	
Primary objective(s)	Define the primary objective(s) of your project. Shortly present the hypotheses and detailed research questions if applicable at this stage.
Secondary objective(s)	Define the possible secondary objective(s) for your project. Shortly present the hypotheses and detailed research questions if applicable at this stage.
Expected outcomes / Impact	
Outcome / Impact	After finishing your study, what are the expected outcomes and possible impact.

Figure 10 Word Living Lab Research Protocol Template

Description

Material describes a template for describing living lab research protocol in different living lab technology readiness levels (TRLs). Material includes excel- and word-template as well as an example for a study developing physical fitness testing service for aging persons. The template is grounded on Hoffmann et al. (2014) template for intervention description and replication and seeks answers to following dimensions:

1) Study title, 2) Study rationale / background and significance, 3) Study objective(s), 4) Expected outcomes / Impact, 5) Inclusion and exclusion criteria, 6) sample size, 7) recruitment plan, 8) What (procedures and methods), 9) What (materials, technologies and devices), 10) Where (Research environment), 11) How, 12) When and how much (Scheduling, date and duration), 13) Who provides (Research team and their roles) and 14) Ethical considerations and issues

Hoffmann, T.C., Glasziou, P.P., Boutron, I., Milne, R., Perera, R., Moher, D., Altman, D.G., Barbour, V., Macdonald, H., Johnston, M. and Lamb, S.E., 2014. Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide. Bmj, 348.

Audience: Persons planning a living lab research project

Purpose: Create robust research plan for living lab project

Key outcomes: Template provides structured plan to conduct and communicate living lab project activities.

Skills Survey for Master course webinar series participants

Excel-template

Description

Questionnaire collected information on skills and knowledge relating Innovate to Thrive: Mastering Living Labs and Collaborative Innovation webinar series topics. Skills and knowledge are evaluated by using 5-point Likert scale (Very poor, Poor, Acceptable, Good, very good). Survey consist 22 question covering following topics: 1) Innovation Strategy, 2) Living Lab Methodology, 3) Collaborative Innovation, 4) Design Thinking, 5) Prototype Development, 6) User-Centric Research, 7) Data Analysis, 8) Project Management, 9) Business Model Innovation, 10) Technology Integration, 11) Entrepreneurship Skills, 12) Market Validation, 13) Stakeholder Engagement, 14) Ethical Innovation, 15) Communication and Presentation, 16) Risk Management, 17) Financial Acumen, 18) Leadership and Teamwork, 19) Networking and Collaboration, 20) Critical Thinking, 21) Adaptability and Resilience, 22) Legal and Intellectual Property Knowledge.

Audience: All participants

Purpose: Gain understanding on who is participating and what kind of skills they have

Key outcomes: Template provides structured plan to conduct and communicate living lab project activities.

Participants skills and knowledge profile covering 22 variables.

FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) quiz

Excel-template

Description

Quiz includes 40 true or false question on FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) topics. Participant can take the Quiz as many times they want. After submitting answers total score and correct answers are shown. After submitting answers, the correct answers and feedback (if the individual answer was correct or incorrect) is presented.

Audience: Persons testing their knowledge on FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Purpose: Self-learning tool to check your knowledge on FAIR data and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Key outcomes: Self-testing your knowledge on sustainability topics.

5 REPOSITORY ONLINE MATERIALS

5.1 Structure Repository Online Materials

All educational resources can be accessed within the repository hosted on the project's website and the Slideshare dedicated to the project.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the VITALISE project has demonstrated significant achievement through its WP4 activities, generating over 100 learning materials encompassing presentations, printable templates, exercises, and digital tools. These resources serve as invaluable assets in advancing knowledge dissemination and skill development within the project's scope. The breadth and depth of these materials underscore the project's commitment to fostering learning and innovation, thereby contributing to its overall success and impact. Moving forward, the utilization and further development of these resources promise to continue enriching the learning experience and driving progress within the VITALISE project and beyond.

It's promising to note that the content from programs such as the Summer School and Master Course Webinars will be repurposed for use in sister projects and within the Living Lab community of ENOLL. This initiative not only maximizes the value of the existing materials but also ensures their continued relevance and impact across related endeavours. By leveraging these resources, sister projects and Living Labs can benefit from the expertise and insights cultivated within the VITALISE framework, fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing within the research community. This strategic approach underscores the commitment to efficiency, sustainability, and the continual advancement of research and innovation objectives across multiple initiatives.

7 References

VITALISE. (2023). *Summer School Internal report*. Brussels, Belgium: VITALISE.

DELIVERABLE D4.1 Online and Printed Educational Materials first version

8 APPENDICES

8.1 ANNEX 1 Summer School Agenda 2022

Agenda

VITALISE
Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

VITALISE Summer School 2022
Agenda for Day 1 (6 July 2022)
Living Labs methods & tools for researchers

- 09:00 - 10:00**
Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Francesca Spagnoli
ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs
 - Welcome and objectives
 - Living Labs basics, benefits and challenges
- 10:00 - 11:00**
Despoina Petsani
AUTH - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
 - How researchers can be involved and use Living Labs in their daily job: case studies
- 11:00 - 12:00**
Session moderated by Leidy Enriquez
ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs
 - Tour de table: get to know each other
- 12:00 - 13:00**
Teemu Santonen
LAUREA University of Applied Sciences
 - Living Lab innovation processes and services
- 13:00 - 14:00**
Lunch Break
- 14:00 - 16:00**
Session moderated by Teemu Santonen
LAUREA University of Applied Sciences
 - Hands on exercise on selected methods & services for small research design and peer to peer learning
- 16:00**
Excursion to the Acropolis Museum and dinner (optional)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

VITALISE
Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure

VITALISE Summer School 2022
Agenda for Day 2 (7 July 2022)
Co-creating with Living Labs to improve your research

- 10:00 - 11:00**
Alexandra Anagnostopoulou
AUTH - Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
 - Data ownership within Living Labs
- 11:00 - 12:00**
Beatriz Merino
UPM - Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
 - Experimentation & co-creation in a real-life environment
- 12:00 - 13:00**
Session moderated by Beatriz Merino
UPM - Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
 - Hands on exercise: co-creation session on your selected research cases
- 13:00 - 14:00**
Lunch Break
- 14:00 - 15:30**
Eva Kehayia
McGill University
 - How to change my research through Living Labs
- 15:30 - 16:30**
Inspirational session with representatives from **LifeChamps** and other research projects where Living Labs were included.
- 16:30 - 17:30**
Joint SALL & VITALISE Summer School Workshop

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

8.2 ANNEX 12 Summer School Agenda 2023

Summer School Program

Day 3: 08 June 2023

**VITALISE
SUMMER SCHOOL
2023**

Summer School Program

Day 3 | Thursday 08 June 2023

Developing your own research through Living Labs

Timeslot	Session
09:15 - 09:30	Registrations & Welcome
09:30 - 10:00	Icebreaker and get to know each other
10:00 - 10:30	Living Labs 101: benefits, pitfalls, and challenges
10:30 - 11:00	Creating research through Living Labs
11:00 - 11:30	Living Labs innovation process and services
11:30 - 13:00	Hands on session: Emerging research design and innovation processes through LL
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 - 15:00	Living Labs Governance & Business models
15:00 - 16:00	Experimentation, stakeholder engagement & co-creation in Living Labs through case studies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017696. This material reflects only the author's view and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Day 4: 09 June 2023

**VITALISE SUMMER SCHOOL
2023**

Summer School Program

Day 4 | Friday 09 June 2023

Putting the life into your Living Lab: VITALISE Tools

Timeslot	Session
09:30 - 10:00	Welcome and introduction of the second day
10:00 - 11:00	Harmonization of the Health and Wellbeing Living Lab process and ICT tools
11:00 - 12:00	Hands-on workshop on VITALISE system for data discovery and analysis
12:00 - 13:00	Workshop on the VITALISE Living Lab Lexicon
13:00 - 13:30	Wrap up, opportunities for collaboration and conclusions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017696. This material reflects only the author's view and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

8.3 ANNEX 3 Bootcamp Agenda 2023

Commercialization Bootcamp Program

Day 1: 06 June 2023

**Participants need to bring their laptops!*

Commercialization Bootcamp Program

Day 1 Tuesday 06 June 2023	
09:30 - 10:00	Welcome
10:00 - 10:30	Real-world Commercialization Successes & Challenges
10:30 - 11:00	Scaling up from a R&D project to a real business case: ReMember-Me Project
11:00 - 11:30	Pathways for Commercialization
11:30 - 11:45	Coffee Break
11:45 - 12:00	User / Customer Profiling
12:00 - 13:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Group Work #1: User Profiling and customer needs Group Work #2: Problem - Solution Fit
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 - 15:00	Revenue Models Group Work #3: Identifying Revenue Streams
15:00 - 16:00	Discussion & Reflections

**Participants need to bring their laptops!*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017966. This material reflects only the author's view and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained.

Day 2: 07 June 2023

**Participants need to bring their laptops!*

Commercialization Bootcamp Program

Day 2 Wednesday 07 June 2023	
09:30 - 10:15	Assessment tools for commercialization potential + Example
10:15 - 10:45	Leveraging Your Intellectual Property: licensing and other issues
10:45 - 11:30	Investment Basics for Tech Startups: Funding Cycles & Structures
11:30 - 11:45	Coffee Break
11:45 - 13:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loop Diagnostics: Startup Commercialization Case Study Discussion & Q/A
13:00	Lunch and Departure for Excursion to LL

**Participants need to bring their laptops!*

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